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PROGRESS REPORT M18

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Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review/ have reviewed the current document.

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Delivery Deadline	Actual delivery (Done by)
1	Submission of Internal Draft Deliverable to reviewers and uploading on Research Participant Portal	28/03/19	28/03/19
2	Initial Review and Comments obtained	29/03/19	29/03/19
3	Uploading of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal and submission	31/03/19	31/03/19

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports briefly on the overall progress of project FreeWheel at month 18, specifying also technical, administrative and financial progress.

Overall progress

The project started October the 1st, 2017 and it is now at the end of its Month 18. The workpackages active at the end of M18 are:

1. WP1 “Project Management” (M1-36);
2. WP3 “FreeWheel product design” (M6-M24);
3. WP4 “FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design” (M12-29);
4. WP5 “FreeWheel process design” (M12-M27);
5. WP6 “FreeWheel production infrastructure” (M12-M25);
6. WP9 “FreeWheel dissemination and exploitation”

WP2 “Human centred requirements and objectives” concluded at M12, while WP7 “FreeWheel integration and lifecycle distributed management and optimization” just started. WP8 “FreeWheel demonstration” is starting at M24.

Technical progress

WP2 concluded with a definition of the design and functional requirements of the FreeWheel solution. This translated mainly in a definition of the technical and service delivery objectives which have informed the design of the FreeWheel product and service (WP3 and WP4). WP3 made progress in the design of the motorisation solution comprehensive of sensoring to aid autonomous drive, as well as on the engineering platform to be used to exchange CAD files on the solution itself. FreeWheel product includes commercial components and customised parts that could be made by Additive Manufacturing and 3DPrinting exploiting the experience and technological capabilities and facilities within the Consortium (WP5 and WP6). WP4 concentrated on the definition of the service blueprint and digital touchpoints, with work starting on the app to accompany the user during the FreeWheel experience. WP9 activities covered awareness raising initiatives including the set up of @FreeWheelEU Twitter profile and undertook the first mapping off exploitable results.

Administrative progress

The 18 months Review Meeting was held in Brussels on March the 26th, where the Consortium presented the work done to date to the Project Monitor and the Project Officer.

Deliverables expected in the third semester of the project have all been uploaded, while only one milestone (MS13 Specification of Exploitable Results) was due in the period (M18).

Financial progress

Project spent at M18 is configured as a 42% of total personnel cost and 31% of total “Other Direct Costs”.

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Introduction

This document reports on overall progress of project FreeWheel, covering the third semester of the project (October 2018 – March 2019) and analysing technical, administrative and financial progress.

The project started October the 1st, 2017 and has now reached mid point. The active workpackages are:

1. WP1 “Project Management” (M1-36);
2. WP3 “FreeWheel product design” (M6-M24);
3. WP4 “FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design” (M12-29);
4. WP5 “FreeWheel process design” (M12-M27);
5. WP6 “FreeWheel production infrastructure” (M12-M25);
6. WP9 “FreeWheel dissemination and exploitation”

WP2 “Human centred requirements and objectives” concluded at M12, while WP7 “FreeWheel integration and lifecycle distributed management and optimization” just started. WP8 “FreeWheel demonstration” is starting at M24.

The partners are all fully cooperating to ensure the progress of the project, and the FreeWheel solution is taking shape both in terms of product (motorising solution) and service (users experience).

Technical content

WP3: FreeWheel product design

The main objective of this WP focuses on the design of the FreeWheel mobility mechatronic solution consisting of the active module (the motor) and the customised connectors. A prototype of the solution was tested to validate the active system and to study the range of the battery pack installed to power the motor.

The solution is equipped with a wide range of sensors to allow for the control of the motor and the stability of the system as well as to aid autonomous driving.

The Lifecycle Engineering platform is being developed and allows for the uploading, downloading and managing of the CAD files related to wheelchairs and FreeWheel solution accessories. The platform includes also a full 3D visualisation of the CAD files.

WP4 FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design

The work package fulfills two main objectives: (1) designing FreeWheel service and (2) design and implement the digital touch points for the correct service provisioning.

The workpackage delivered the Service Design Challenges which are shaping the definition of the service. A blueprint of the service, i.e. a graphical representation of the relationships between different service components (people, processes), which are directly tied to the touchpoints, is being finalised, while the features of the digital touchpoint (the FreeWheel app) have been defined and are currently being implemented.

WP5 FreeWheel process design and WP6 FreeWheel production infrastructure

While the FreeWheel product is being finalised in its first design, the Consortium has reviewed and shared the technical capabilities and facilities available. The WP5 and WP6 teams have built up during the years a wealth of experience in the application of Additive Manufacturing technologies, through design and construction of innovative equipment (e.g. H2020 project Borealis direct energy deposition machine) and study of process parameters to obtain a variety of features (thin walls, bored blocks, dense shapes) and functional parts (brackets and flanges). Also commercial machines are available to cover the production of the FreeWheel demonstrators and trial the process and production chain which would be required to deliver a commercial product. Furthermore, the team includes a specialist 3dPrinting company who are able to build structural and non structural components in a variety of materials including carbon fibre composites. The adaptive CAx design framework is under development and the aesthetic part design methodology was developed as well as a model based on RAMI4.0 applied to plastics supporting the 3D Printing activities undertaken.

WP9 FreeWheel Dissemination and Exploitation

Awareness raising about the project has continued with participation to a number of events (MEDICA in Dusseldorf, International Day of people with Disability in Lugano, specialised training events in Patras) and the opening and management of a FreeWheel project twitter profile. Some three papers are under preparation, including one on context awareness in use phase and one on process planning for plastics, while the subjects for a number of collaborative White papers have been identified. Participation to conferences has also been identified as a possible dissemination outlet to reach also industrial audiences. With respect to the exploitation, work is being undertaken to develop the specification of exploitable results which will inform Milestone 13 and following work on this area.

Administrative Progress

The 18 months Review Meeting was held in Brussels on March the 26th, where the Consortium presented the work done to date to the Project Monitor and the Project Officer.

Deliverables expected in the third semester of the project have all been uploaded, while only one milestone (MS13 Specification of Exploitable Results) was due in the period (M18).

As the project has reached mid point and has undergone its first and only planned Review, a fully detailed technical and financial report will be prepared for the EU Commission by the end of May 2019.

Financial Progress

Project spent at M18 is configured as a 42% of total personnel cost and 31% of total "Other Direct Costs". The personnel expenditure is in line with the theoretical plan (46%) while the amount of other costs is as expected for a project delivering two demonstrators as final outcomes.

Conclusions

Project FreeWheel is progressing overall in line with expectations. With the finalisation of the definition of the FreeWheel product, the activities for its production – definition of process and definition of production infrastructure – are aligning, both for metal and plastic parts. The definition of the FreeWheel service is well underway and the accompanying app is currently being developed. A first map of exploitable results is under definition to develop a strong exploitation plan.

The fifth GA is to be held in the period September-October 2019..